

ISic1102

I.Sicily inscription 1102

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

See December 2018 (Metcalfe)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Drepanum

Place of origin (modern)

Trapani

Provenance

Said to come from the Chiesa di San Andrea Apostolo, Bonagia

Coordinates

38.0490478,12.6126099

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Erice, Biblioteca Civica "Vito Carvini", inventory 212

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Ῥο]ῦφον
2. Νεικόμαχο[ν]
3. Ἰουλιανὸν
4. λαμπρότατον
5. ὑπάτον
6. ἀνθύπατον
7. Ἀσίας
8. δικαίωτατον
9. Ἀσίννιος
10. Ἀμίαντος
11. ἐπίτροπος
12. τὸν δεσπότη[ν]

Apparatus

Brugnone 1982-83 suggests a line preceding: [Γ Ἀσίννιον]; Manganaro argues that the top of the stone is partially preserved

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284825

EDCS 39102260

PHI 140586

PHI 331120

Bibliography

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